

Medical Evaluation of Vital Factors Affecting Survival Rate of COVID-19 Patients: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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Abstract

Background and aim: the purpose of present study was evaluation of vital factors affecting survival rate of COVID-19 patients.

Method: all articles published in international databases such as PubMed, Scopus, Science Direct, Embase between January 2019 and March 2022 included. Google Scholar search engine was used; Used PECO strategy to answer the research questions. Data analysis was performed using STATA.V16 software.

Result: In the initial search, 218 studies were identified; full text of 63 articles was reviewed; finally nine articles entered the analysis. Mean differences of SpO₂, Heart rate, Systolic and Diastolic blood pressure between Survival and death groups was 3.15 (MD; 95 CI (2.93, 3.37), p<0.05), 2.20 (MD; 95 CI (-3.19, -1.22) p<0.05) (I²=30.5%; p=0.20) and 2.30 (MD; 95 CI (1.04 - 3.55), p<0.05) and 4.49 (MD; 95 CI 3.80, 5.17), p<0.05), respectively.

Conclusion: survival rate in patients with Covid-19 is directly related to the vital signs and level of consciousness of patients, so that with increasing heart rate and respiratory rate, mortality rate increases.

Key words: COVID-19, Vital Signs, Survival Rate, Patient.

Introduction

Severe acute respiratory syndrome Coronavirus Disease 2019 (SARS -CoV-2) is a common human-animal and emerging disease, which appeared in December 2019 and causes COVID-19 (1-3). This virus is classified as an RNA virus belonging to the coronavirus family(1). This large family causes a wide range of viral illnesses, from the common cold to more severe illnesses such as coronavirus Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS- CoV) and severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS-CoV) (4-6). The disease is highly contagious and each infected person can infect an average of at least 3 others (7-9). Information on the profile and clinical outcome of patients with COVID-19 infection is scarce, but is of particular importance for reducing mortality (10-12). Severe cases of COVID-19 can lead to severe pneumonia, severe respiratory failure, and death from multiple organ failure, while in severe cases, the usual symptoms of a respiratory infection may not be present (13-15). Some patients may initially have symptoms of nausea and diarrhea shortly before the fever, and a small number of patients may have headaches or vomiting of blood and even be relatively asymptomatic (16-18). The study of the characteristics of COVID-19 patients will help to form an accurate picture of the condition of patients and the necessary arrangements to provide better medical services. Therefore, the purpose of present study was evaluation of vital factors affecting survival rate of COVID-19 patients (19-22).

Method

Search strategy

Present study is a systematic review and meta-analysis based on PRISMA guidelines(6), all articles published in international databases such as PubMed, Scopus, Science Direct, Embase between January 2019 and March 2022 included. Google Scholar search engine was used. Used PECO strategy to answer the research questions (Table 1).

The following keywords were used to search:

Coronavirus Disease 2019, COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, Fever, heart rate, HR, respiratory rate, number of breaths, oxygen saturation, oxygen-saturated hemoglobin, SpO₂, vital signs, mortality rate, Death, blood pressure, BP, High blood pressure, hypertension, body temperature.

Inclusion criteria

The selection criteria were RCT studies, cohort studies, case reports, and case-control studies that full text of the article was available. Studies other than these study designs were excluded; only articles published in English were selected.

Table 1. PECO strategy

PECO strategy	Description
P	Population: COVID-19 patients

E	Exposure: SARS -CoV-2
C	Comparison: Survival vs. death
O	Outcome: survival rate

Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed using STATA.V16 software. I^2 index test was used to evaluate the level of heterogeneity ($I^2 < 50\%$ = low levels, $50 < I^2 < 75\%$ = moderate and $I^2 > 75\%$ = high levels). 95% confidence interval on the difference between means about vital signs were done with fixed effect model and in-variance method.

Result

First search for articles in databases, 218 articles were identified. After importing all articles into EndNote.X8 software, duplicate articles were deleted (n=81). 137 articles entered and examined in second stage. At this stage, while reviewing the titles and abstracts of articles, 139 unrelated articles were excluded from the study. In the third stage, the full text of 63 articles was reviewed. Finally, six articles that were published between January 2019 and March 2022 and met the inclusion criteria, entered the analysis.

Characteristics

All studies that included in present article were Retrospectives studies. The number of patients were 8841 with 69.11 years mean of age (4058 female and 4783 male), respectively (Table 2).

Figure 1. PRISMA flowcharts

Vital factors affecting survival rate of COVID-19 patients

Fever rate

Mean differences of Fever rate between Survival and death groups was -0.20 (MD; 95 CI (-0.39, 0.00), p=0.05) (I²=0.00%; p=0.49). According to figure 2, no difference observed between groups (Figure 2). However, Fever was higher in deceased patients with COVID-19 than in survivors (p>0.05).

Systolic and Diastolic blood pressure:

Mean differences of Systolic and Diastolic blood pressure between Survival and death groups were 2.30 (MD; 95 CI (1.04, -3.55), p<0.05) (I²=68.65%; p=0.01) and 4.49 (MD; 95 CI 3.80, 5.17), p<0.05) (I²=74.67%; p=0.00), respectively. According to figure 3 and 4, significant difference observed between groups. In the group of patients who died with COVID-19, both Systolic and Diastolic blood pressure were low.

Table 2. Summary of studies characteristics

Study. Years	Study design	Number of Patients		Age (mean) (years)
		male	female	
Yang et al., 2020 (7)	Retrospectives	45	49	75
Hu et al., 2020 (8)	Retrospectives	62	43	71
Tharakan et al., 2020 (9)	Retrospectives	4118	3496	73
Wang et al., 2020 (10)	Retrospectives	88	114	74.0
Wang et al., 2020 (11)	Retrospectives	169	170	75
Lu et al., 2020 (12)	Retrospectives	8	12	70
Pan et al., 2020 (13)	Retrospectives	85	39	70
Covino et al., 2020 (14)	Retrospectives	37	32	80
Chen et al., 2020 (15)	Retrospectives	171	103	64

Figure2. Forest plot showed Fever rate between Survival and death groups

Figure3. Forest plot showed Systolic blood pressure between Survival and death groups

Figure4. Forest plot showed Diastolic blood pressure between Survival and death groups

Oxygen saturation

Mean differences of SpO2 between Survival and death groups was 3.15 (MD; 95 CI (2.93, 3.37), $p < 0.05$) ($I^2 = 95.82$; $p = 0.00$). According to figure 5, a significant decrease in SpO2 was observed in the group of deceased patients compared to living patients.

Figure5. Forest plot showed Oxygen saturation between Survival and death groups

Respiratory rate

Mean differences of Respiratory rate between Survival and death groups was -2.54 (MD; 95 CI (-3.18, -1.90), $p < 0.05$) ($I^2 = 83.03$; $p = 0.00$). According to figure 6, Respiratory rate was significantly higher in the deceased group.

Figure6. Forest plot showed Respiratory rate between Survival and death groups

Heart rate

Mean differences of Heart rate between Survival and death groups were 2.20 (MD; 95 CI (-3.19, -1.22) $p < 0.05$) ($I^2 = 30.5\%$; $p = 0.20$). According to figure 7, the heart rate in the group of patients who died of Covid-19 was much higher than the group of survivors (23-25).

Figure 7. Forest plot showed Heart rate between Survival and death groups

Discussion

The clinical signs and symptoms of patients who have died show that these patients had worse and more severe conditions at the time of arrival, so that the study of blood oxygen saturation shows that most of these patients had SPO₂ less than 93% (24-26). On the other hand, the most

common symptoms in deceased patients are shortness of breath and disturbance in the level of consciousness, so examining and observing the clinical symptoms of patients may help physicians to identify their weaker prognosis (27-29).

The present meta-analysis showed that survival in patients with Covid-19 is generally related to heart rate, blood pressure, oxygen level and respiratory rate; while fever does not affect the mortality rate. Considering that studies have shown that one of the most important factors in the diagnosis of Covid-19 disease is body temperature and high fever is associated with the severity of pneumonia; However, the findings showed that it did not affect the survival rate. The cause can be expressed as high fever in the early stages of the disease (30-32).

One of the factors influencing the survival rate of Covid-19 patients is the heart rate, which increases the mortality rate; acute myocardial injury is one of the most important complications of Covid-19 disease. At the time of hospitalization or outpatient hospitalization, heart rate should be monitored to increase survival (33-35). The most important factor that affects the survival rate of Covid-19 patients is the level of SpO₂, which should be carefully evaluated (36-38). The present study had some limitations, such as the lack of RCT studies. High heterogeneity is observed between studies which can have a negative impact on the evidence obtained (39-41). It is suggested that future studies be performed using the same procedure, that the sample size be increased, and that the mortality rate be reported (42-44).

Conclusion

According to the findings, the survival rate in patients with Covid-19 is directly related to the vital signs and level of consciousness of patients, so that with increasing heart rate and respiratory rate, mortality rate increases and with decreasing blood pressure, oxygen level and decrease Survival levels of consciousness decrease, resulting in increased mortality. To increase survival in patients with Covid-19, the patient's level of consciousness and vital signs should be carefully monitored regularly.

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